

Beginning of a New Era: With AI-based CHATBOTS

Benett Varghese Thomas, J.Juanita Anabel & Nia James

Department of Commerce, Madras Christian College

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Abstract

Communication, as the word itself denotes, is all about common understanding. Problems arise due to ineffective communication. Common understanding is required in every field. Especially for business, it is very important that they bend according to the needs of the customers in order to satisfy them. And so, the customer service industry has come up with an innovation of theirs-CHATBOTS. Chatbots are a form of computer application based on AI (artificial intelligence) which provides a real conversation with the users. This paper analyses the working of chatbots and its future scope. Primary data were collected using questionnaire from about 121 respondents which included students (male and female) from Madras Christian college and their parents who were working in Chennai. And the data was analysed using statistical tools like pie diagrams and graphs. This research would analyse the presence of chatbots in the present generation along with its benefits in order to measure its extent of growth in the future.

Introduction

Chatbots are a form of computer application which provides real conversation with users. They carry out conversations with its users, convincing them that they were conversing with humans and not machines.

The early life of chatbots begins from Joseph Weizenbaum’s ELIZA program (1966). He was a professor at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT). He named the program as Eliza, a character in Pygmalion. (It’s a play about a Cockney girl who learns to speak and think like an upper-class lady.) Also, he was successful in making his users believe that they were talking to humans and not machines. The term chatbot comes from “chatterbot,” a name given by inventor Michael Mauldi (1994). The creator of Julia, the first chatbot made with Verbot, a popular software program and development kit. Today, AI chatbots are also known by different other names such as talkbot, bot, IM bot, intelligent chatbot, conversation bot, AI conversation bot, talking bot, interactive agent, artificial conversation entity, or virtual talk chatbot. Chatbots are already part of virtual assistants, in Customer Care Services.

Artificial intelligence (in the form of natural-language processing, machine learning etc) makes it possible for chatbots to “learn” by discovering patterns in data. Without training, these chatbots can apply the pattern to similar problems. This ability gives them the “intelligence” to perform tasks, solve problems, and manage information without human intervention.

Objectives

1. To identify the awareness about chatbot assistance included in customer services.
2. To analyse its benefits to the users.
3. To know the extent of customer satisfaction offered by chatbots.

Review of Literature

According to “A Tool of Conversation: Chatbot” by M. Dahiya, Chatbot helps the user by answering the questions asked by them and they can easily type their query in natural language and retrieve information. The development and improvement of chatbot design grow at an unpredictable rate due to variety of methods and approaches used to design a chatbot.

In Amir Shevat’s “The bot rulebook” (slack platform blog) his guiding mission is about: “A bot’s mission is to make human life better, to provide a helping hand, and to do so proficiently and courteously.”

According to “A nice and friendly chat with a bot: User perceptions of ai based service agents” by Nancy and Stefanie, AI-based service agents interact in a similar way as humans in human-to-human chat conversations, but instead of a live person on the other end, a chat bot steers the communication based on artificial intelligence and Natural Language Interaction.

Methodology

The study is conducted to grasp the potential of chatbots, understand how they work, what their capabilities are and its future scope. Survey method is used for collecting data with the help of questionnaire. The study is conducted in Chennai, Tambaram region. A sample of 121 was selected using the convenience sampling method. It shows response rate of 100%. The sample includes students from Madras Christian college and other working-class individuals, who gave their view on chatbots, its performance, popularity and progress. Their valuable response determines the reliability of this survey. The primary data collected was interpreted into pie diagrams and graphs. The source for secondary data includes journals and articles from, articles, internet and other sources.

Data and Interpretation

The data collected to identify the awareness of chatbots included in Customer Services are as follows:

The above chart states that majority of the samples are aware of chatbots and are aware of chatbot being included in customer services. This concludes that consumers have used the aid of chatbots and are more familiar with chatbots through customer services.

The data collected to analyse the benefits of chatbots to the customers are as follows:

Rate your chatbot in providing actionable solutions?
121 responses

The above data collected, indicates that the customer is willing to get quick, accurate and actionable solutions that highlights the various benefits that customers had gained, using chatbots.

The data collected to know the Customer Satisfaction is as follows:

The above charts explain that 46% to 49% of customers are moderate about their satisfaction towards chatbot assistance in customer services and 41% to 49% of customers satisfied towards chatbot assistance in customer services.

Finding

According to the data collected and interpreted we see that people have accepted the assistance of chatbots in customer services. Majority of the samples feel neutral about its assistance which denotes the beginning of this new era with Chatbots in customer services and marketing. The following is the summary of the data collected.

They all agree that instant, time saving and accurate solutions are needed in the Customer Care Services.

- As chatbot can cater a huge amount of target audience 24/7, people are aided anytime which is appreciated among customers.
- Multilingual chatbots reduce the hiring expenses of different language resources.

Conclusion

The research shows that inclusion of chatbots in customer care services has begun as a good start. It has developed the way customer problems and queries are rectified to the optimum satisfaction of consumers. However, this new start has been neutral among customers in view of its future scope in E-commerce.

Thus, we conclude that among the samples, 43.6% of them are neutral, 39.7% agree and 8.3% strongly agree about chatbot's future in E-Commerce. However, they still feel the need of human assistance in various grounds. Thus, the entrepreneurs have to take various steps in emphasising improvements in these AI based Chatbot assistance in customer services for the fullest of customer satisfaction.

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